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Abstract: This articles discusses and summaries a number of notions related to text linguistics that helps language learners how read texts and analyze them critically, and suggests some useful strategies to improve reading comprehension.

Key words: Text linguistics, persuasive elements, paradigmatic and syntagmatic axes, speech levels, language level.

Today, Linguistics is associated with all levels of language has made significant strides in problem research. Research into text and its nature dates back to the mid- 20th century began to appear. The status of the text, its role in the language system and what to start with in linguistic analysis of the text the linguist’s answers to the questions are also intertwined less compatible. For example, setting the status of the text, we sometimes have different on the issue. Text what is the nature of the characters, to call the text a speech process whether or not to interpret the text as a result of speech process whether by linking the text to oral or written speech. There are also different views on whether to study perspective. Normally, texts are studied according to their structures, principles of text formation, perceptions, methods of text analysis, etc. Text linguistics is the subject of many linguists attracted attention. Such as, Russian linguists: A.A. Potebnya, Z.V. Scherba. V.V. Vinogradov, M.M. Bakhtin, O. Moskalskaya and foreign linguists: M.M. Bakhtin, R. Jakobson, Z. Harris. V.Matezius, F.Danesh, V.Dressler, P.Hartman, I.Kovtunova, I.Galperin, K.Gauzenblas, N.Pospelov, T. Silman, N.Shvedova, K. Solganik, L.loseva and Uzbek linguists: K. Abdullayev, N. Navro’zova, M. Qurbonova, M. Yo’ldoshev and others.

“Discourse analysis” was the first work to mark of the beginning of text linguistics which was written by Harris in 1952. He expressed several ideas in this work remain significant for the present day linguistics and stated “language is presented not in the form of separate words or sentences but in the form of a text” which was remained us the main conception of text linguistics. After him, many linguists made huge contributions to the development of text linguistics. One of the most noticeable work is “Текст как объект лингвистического исследования” (1981) by I. R. Galperin covered with a wide range of questions such as the definition of text, text categories, text units, text parameters, etc. The author states that the notion of text being very complicated and multifold should be analysed from different angles including static and dynamic aspects, paradigmatic and syntagmatic axes, language and speech levels, semantic and structural planes of the text. According to I.R. Galperin grammatical methods of analysis can be applied to the text. As is known, grammar tends to trace certain regularities out of multiple, and seemingly chaotic language usage. Similarly, any text despite its unique and individual character is subordinated to some rules, principles, models and regularities. For this reason, so much attention is attached to text categories constituting the essence of any text. I.R. Galperin considers a great number of text categories such as informativity, segmentation, cohesion, continuum, prospection, and retrospection, modality, integration and completeness. Each category has been subjected to a scrupulous analysis providing a sufficient grounding for convincing conclusions.

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A Russian scholar M.V. Lyapon describes the text according to the following four signs indicates that it can be based on:

of worth mentioning work is "Introduction to the text linguistics" by K. A. de Dressler. This work is based on the solutions to the problem of textuality which presenting seven standards: *cohesion, coherence, intentionality, acceptability, informativity, situationality, intertextuality*.

Lyapon states that the most important of human factors in text formation is one of the factors, a living source human text for human text formation. Z.Y. Turaeva in her course reading — "Лингвистика текста" is concerned with a number of issues impossible to miss to a scholarly content. She investigates the structure of literary writings separating its models: profound and shallow, vertical and horizontal. Much consideration is paid to content categories, especially to those that remain uncultivated, for case, the category of space and time. One major advantage of this book is that it has formulated the tasks of text linguistics:

- to study text as a system of a high rank, characterized by cohesion and integrity;
- to build up text typology according to the communicative and linguistic characteristics;
- to explore text units constituting text;
- to examine text categories, their distinctive features, taxonomy and hierarchy;
- to analyze the peculiarities of language units functioning within the framework of the text;
- to specify inter phrase links and relations, viz. structural, semantic and other means of cohesion between text components.

Literary, the notion of text has been studying for centuries. In order to delve deeper into the concept of text, let us consider the history and etymology of its origin. **Text** - "wording of anything written," from Old French *texte*, Old North French *tixte* "text, book; Gospels", from Medieval Latin *textus* "the Scriptures, text, treatise," in Late Latin "written account, content, characters used in a document," from Latin *textus* "style or texture of a work," literally "thing woven," from past participle stem of *texere* "to weave, to join, fit together, braid, interweave, construct, fabricate, build," from PIE root **teks** - "to weave, to fabricate, to make; make wicker or wattle framework." Almost all linguists use the word "text" tries to define this concept in one way or another. According to Werlich, E., *A text grammar of English*: "A text is an extended structure of [syntactic units](#) [i. e. text as super-sentence] such as words, groups, and clauses and textual units that is marked by both [coherence](#) among the elements and completion ... [Whereas] a non-text consists of random sequences of linguistic units such as sentences, paragraphs, or sections in any temporal and/or spatial extension." While Halliday and Hasan comment on the notion of the text is A text is a unit of language in use. It is not a grammatical unit, like a [clause](#) or a sentence; and

it is not defined by its size... A text is best regarded as a *semantic* unit; a unit not of form but of meaning. Fowler says: A text is made up of sentences, but there exist separate principles of text-construction, beyond the rules for making sentences. Text is a multi-faceted, complex device, so for the semiotic, which is not peculiar to him in its description, communicative, structural, pragmatic, cognitive, nominative feature needs to be taken into account. Otherwise in other words, no description is as complex as any text one-sided cannot describe perfectly. So everyone relative to the text event of the researcher or group of researchers a unique perspective is formed and the research planned subject to this view. Given the text event, it's hard to disagree with any of your definitions because it's a link in each of which one or another aspect of the text phenomenon is illuminated, i.e., each one aspect of the object under study in one observation is its own finds expression. In the initial researches, the views on the text were mainly expressed in terms of its structure and the similarities and differences between the other languages, which were mainly aimed at defining the boundaries of the text. Indeed, the issue of setting a text boundary is a very important requirement in the definition. It can be possibly given the limit of the text show by counting species. For example: *novel, pamphlet, story, article, letter, dialogue* and etc. The concept of "structure" in the philosophical interpretation of the integrity of the object and a description of the stable traits and relationships that sustain it, in which the structure of the text is in the communicative content of the linguistic form as a "trace" left in the statement of the opposite or fact piece can be calculated. The boundary of the text is content and form relations are determined on the basis of dialectics. This relationship is equally reflected in the inner and outer aspects of the text. That's it because when it comes to grammatical analysis of the text, its internal and differentiate the laws of external semantic structure and text in its structure of the internal relations of the component to determine the effect of the appearance of the part on the hierarchical order purpose.

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